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Spatial determination and prognostic impact of the fibroblast transcriptome in pancreatic ductal adenocarcinoma

Authors

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43 **Abstract**

44

45 Pancreatic ductal adenocarcinoma has a poor clinical outcome and responses to
46 immunotherapy are suboptimal. Stromal fibroblasts are a dominant but heterogenous
47 population within the tumor microenvironment and therapeutic targeting of stromal
48 subsets may have therapeutic utility. Here we combine spatial transcriptomics and scRNA-
49 Seq datasets to define the transcriptome of tumor-proximal and tumor-distal cancer-
50 associated fibroblasts (CAFs) and link this to clinical outcome. Tumor-proximal fibroblasts
51 comprise large populations of myofibroblasts, strongly expressed podoplanin, and were
52 enriched for Wnt ligand signaling. In contrast, inflammatory CAFs were dominant within
53 tumor-distal subsets and expressed complement components and the Wnt-inhibitor SFRP2.
54 Poor clinical outcome was correlated with elevated HIF-1 α and podoplanin expression
55 whilst expression of inflammatory and complement genes was predictive of extended
56 survival. These findings demonstrate the extreme transcriptional heterogeneity of CAFs and
57 its determination by apposition to tumor. Selective targeting of tumor-proximal subsets,
58 potentially combined with HIF-1 α inhibition and immune stimulation, may offer a multi-
59 modal therapeutic approach for this disease.

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84 Introduction

85 Therapeutic control of pancreatic ductal adenocarcinoma (PDAC) is one of the greatest
86 challenges in oncology and PDAC remains associated with poor long-term survival (1).
87 Although immunotherapy has transformed the clinical outlook for many tumor subtypes its
88 impact on PDAC has been disappointing to date. One factor in this regard may be the
89 characteristic nature of the PDAC microenvironment which is associated with an intense
90 desmoplastic reaction characterized by an abundance of cancer associated fibroblasts (CAF)
91 (2) (3).

92 Fibroblasts are key regulators of tumor biology and there is now intense interest in
93 understanding how they may act to maintain or suppress tumor growth. CAF are the
94 predominant source of extracellular matrix and develop a complex system of interactions
95 with tumor cells. Although some of the features of CAF suggest feature of chronic activation
96 with sustained production of alpha-small muscle actin (α -SMA), they differ from normal
97 counterparts by relative resistance to apoptosis or reversion of quiescence (4). PDAC-
98 associated CAF can limit the access of immune effector cells to tumor (5-7), promote the
99 infiltration of immune suppressive leucocyte populations and directly support tumor growth
100 (8-11). However, studies from murine models have also shown that fibroblasts may also
101 play a protective role in limiting tumor metastasis and that targeting of stromal cells can
102 accelerate disease progression (12). Furthermore, a clinical trial that targeted CAF through
103 inhibition of the hedgehog protein, combined with chemotherapy, was terminated early
104 due to disease progression (13). One suggestion has been that fibroblasts may play an
105 important role in constraining the growth of of early-stage tumors but subsequently
106 become subverted to support tumor progression (3). As such, effective fibroblast-targeted
107 therapies will need to be directed selectively towards those subpopulations that are critical
108 to support tumor growth.

109 Transcriptional analyses have shown at least four subsets of CAF in PDAC with a
110 heterogenous profile and direct associations with clinical outcome (10). Spatially-related
111 features are also observed with α -SMA^{high} myofibroblast populations closely associated with
112 tumor whilst inflammatory subsets reside more distally (14). Cytokines such as TGF and IL-1
113 appear as key regulators and may direct differentiation from a CD105+ precursor (15).
114 Marked cellular plasticity is a feature of CAF (16) although it remains unclear if CAF develop
115 discrete lineages or are interchangeable. Within PDAC a population of
116 LRRC15⁺ Myofibroblasts is emerging as a potential tumor-associated subset with direct
117 impact on clinical responses to therapy (15).

118 Immunotherapy trials in PDAC indicate that multi-modal approaches may be required for
119 effective therapy and therapeutic targeting of CAF subpopulations could contribute to this.
120 Here we combine spatial transcriptomics with a scRNA-Seq dataset to define the
121 transcriptome of tumor-proximal and tumor-distal fibroblasts within the PDAC
122 microenvironment. Furthermore, these studies were correlated with clinical outcome and
123 revealed that elevated podoplanin and HIF-1 α expression were markers of poor outcome
124 whilst expression of immunoregulatory genes correlates with favorable long-term response.
125 These findings provide insight into stromal architecture in PDAC and could help to guide
126 therapeutic approaches to target pro-tumorigenic fibroblast subsets.
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128 **Results**

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130 **Spatially-defined stromal and immune regions can be characterized within the PDAC**
131 **microenvironment**

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133 Histological slide sections were obtained from tumor biopsies of 24 patients with pancreatic
134 ductal adenocarcinoma (PDAC) who had undergone surgical resection for localized disease.
135 Thirteen patients had died of PDAC within 12 months of diagnosis (subsequently referred to
136 as 'poor response') whilst 11 had survived for at least 36 months ('good response').

137 Four-plex immunofluorescence staining was used initially to define major anatomical
138 subregions of the tumor. Antibodies against pan-cytokeratin, α -SMA and CD45 identified
139 epithelial, fibroblast and immune populations respectively whilst DAPI staining defined
140 nuclear architecture. Regions in which stromal cells were adjacent to tumor ('tumor-
141 proximal stroma'), distant from tumor ('tumor-distal stroma') or enriched for CD45+
142 immune cells ('immune enriched') were then selected and 4 areas ('regions of interest'; ROI)
143 within each of these 3 domains were selected from each patient for assessment using the
144 NanoString GeoMx Digital Spatial Profiler (DSP) platform (**Fig. 1**).

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149 **Fig. 1. Schematic representation of experimental approach**

150 Histological slides of 24 surgical resection specimens from patients with PDAC were stained with
151 DAPI ('nuclear'), anti-pan-CK ('epithelial'), anti- α -SMA ('fibroblast') and anti-CD45 ('immune') to
152 identify tumor cells and primarily to define three domains: 'tumor-proximal stroma' (PS), 'tumor-
153 distant stroma' (DS) and 'immune-enriched' (I). The NanoString Immuno-oncology RNA probe set, in
154 combination with a custom panel of 10 fibroblast-targeted RNA probes, was used to interrogate four
155 areas (termed 'Regions of Interest'; ROI) from each of the 3 domains using the NanoString GeoMx
156 Digital Spatial Profiler (DSP) platform. The transcriptional profile of spatially-defined tumor-proximal
157 or tumor-distant fibroblast cells was subsequently aligned to scRNA-Seq datasets from three
158 additional patients with PDAC.

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161 94 RNA hybridization probes (**Supplementary File 1, Figure 2 – figure supplement 1,2**) for
162 81 endogenous, 6 housekeeping and 7 negative control genes were then applied to the 12
163 ROI from each patient, thus generating 288 transcriptional datasets. Six pan-cytokeratin
164 positive ROI were also selected to define the transcriptional profile of tumor cells.
165 Hierarchical clustering of transcriptional datasets delineated immune and stromal regions
166 with two immune profiles clustering separately due to differential expression of activatory
167 and inhibitory immune genes. Cell-type expression profiles were consistent with immune or
168 stromal origin (**Fig. 2A**). UMAP analysis broadly separated tumor, proximal stroma, distal
169 stroma, and immune regions (**Fig. 2B**) although overlay of clinical outcome data did not
170 reveal significant clustering.
171 Expression of cell lineage marker genes was then used to determine the relative localization
172 of cell subsets within proximal-stromal, distal-stromal, immune or tumor regions of interest
173 (**Fig. 2C**). These confirmed localization of epithelial, fibroblast and lymphoid cells within the
174 tumor, stromal and immune regions respectively whilst monocyte representation was
175 equivalent within stromal and immune regions, consistent with broad infiltration within
176 PDAC microenvironment. CD3E and MS4A1 expression indicated that stromal regions also
177 contained smaller populations of infiltrating T and B cells (**Fig. 2C**). Distinct modules of genes
178 co-expressed with lineage markers could also be identified and were consistent with cell
179 type (**Figure 2 – figure supplement 3**). Stromal regions expressed canonical fibroblast
180 markers such as THY1, PDPN, and FAP whilst immune-specific genes such as PTPRC, CD3E
181 and MS4A1 were present within Immune regions (**Fig. 2 D,E, Figure 2 – figure supplement**
182 **4**).
183 To align the regional transcriptional landscape to specific cell subsets, RNA expression
184 profiles defined by NanoString DSP analysis were mapped onto an additional scRNA-Seq
185 dataset derived from 3 additional patients (**Figure 2 – figure supplement 5**) (17). This
186 revealed that, whilst the great majority of stromal-associated genes were expressed from
187 fibroblasts, the expression of *CSF1R* within stroma was largely derived from myeloid cells,
188 *CTNNA1* localized to endothelial cells and expression of *KRT* was identified as *KRT18* within
189 epithelial cells (**Figure 2 – figure supplement 5C**).
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 192 **Fig.2. Overview of gene expression data from spatially-defined stromal and immune regions**
 193 **within the PDAC tumor microenvironment using NanoString GeoMx DSP**
 194 **A.** Expression profile of all endogenous probes across regions of interest (ROI) with hierarchical
 195 clustering of ROIs.

- 196 **B.** UMAP embedding from normalized count data showing all ROIs overlaid with ROI-specific
197 annotations of Region (Immune/Stroma/Tumor type) and Survival (1yr/3yr).
198 **C.** Mean normalized count of cell type marker genes within regions. Lines indicate regions from the
199 same patient; dashed line represents mean background threshold from negative probes; Mean +/-
200 SE of mean shown in red.
201 **D.** Differential expression analysis to identify genes expressed differentially between Immune and
202 Stroma ROIs. Colored points indicate differentially expressed genes (DEG) (BH adjusted $p < 0.05$ &
203 absolute $\log_2FC > 0.25$).
204 **E.** Immune and Stroma expression signatures from DEGs identified in D.

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208 **The transcriptional profile of stromal regions is strongly determined by proximity to tumor**

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210 We next went on to assess gene expression within stroma in relation to proximity to tumor
211 (**Fig. 3**). Transcriptional profiles were seen to vary markedly between tumor-proximal or
212 tumor-distal ROI. In particular, expression of *DKK3* and *PDPN* was markedly increased in
213 stroma-proximal regions (**Fig. 3A,B,C**) and both are established markers of cancer-
214 associated fibroblasts implicated in support of tumor growth (18-20). In contrast, expression
215 of *C3*, *SFRP2*, *STAT3*, *IL-6* and *THY1* was increased in tumor-distal stroma. *C3* and *SFRP2*
216 expression were particularly elevated (**Fig. 3C**) and localization of *C3* expression to
217 fibroblasts was further suggested by correlation with fibroblast, but not monocyte, marker
218 genes (**Figure 3 – figure supplement 1**). This is noteworthy given the emerging importance
219 for intracellular complement expression and the action of *SFRP2* as a Wnt inhibitor. *STAT3*
220 and *IL-6* expression could be explained by their presence within inflammatory CAFs whilst
221 *THY1* is commonly expressed on stem-like populations of fibroblasts (21). The stem cell
222 marker *CD34* was also expressed in this region (**Fig. 3A,B,C**).

223 Immunohistochemical staining confirmed extreme polarization of podoplanin, *DKK3* and *C3*
224 expression in relation to tumor proximity. Podoplanin was expressed on stroma that
225 encased tumor whilst *DKK3* expression was present both within tumor and tumor-proximal
226 stroma. In contrast, expression of *C3* was localized to distal stroma regions (**Fig. 3D**).

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Fig.3. Expression signature of PDAC tumor-proximal and tumor-distal stromal cells.

A. Differentially expressed genes (DEGs) between stroma regions proximal (P) or distal (D) from tumor. Colored points indicate differentially expressed genes (BH adjusted $p < 0.05$ & absolute $\log_2 FC > 0.25$). **B.** Stroma proximity-to-tumor expression signature from DEGs identified in A. **C.** Relative expression of genes within four PDAC regions: Tumor (T), proximal-tumor stroma (PS), distal-tumor stromal (DS) and immune (I). Lines indicate paired regions from the same patient; dashed line represents mean background threshold from negative probes; Mean \pm SE of mean shown in red. Shown as within patient mean normalized count vs region type for DEG identified in A. **D.** Representative immunohistochemical staining of podoplanin, DKK3 and C3 proteins in relation to tumor cells (T) in PDAC tissue.

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Mapping of spatial transcriptional profiles on to scRNA-Seq reveals key biochemical pathways associated with proximal and distant fibroblasts

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247 Given the profound influence of tumor apposition on the NanoString profile of fibroblasts
248 we were interested to explore global fibroblast transcriptome in relation to spatial
249 localization. The minimal NanoString gene set defining proximal and distant fibroblast
250 subsets was therefore explored within the scRNA-Seq dataset from three additional donors
251 (**Fig. 4A**). Two fibroblast clusters were observed from scRNA-Seq unsupervised clustering
252 analysis and defined as sc-proximal and sc-distal populations due to their distinct proximal
253 and distant gene expression signatures (**Fig. 4B,C**). Transcriptional profiles were highly

254 divergent between proximal compared to distal clusters with 47 genes differentially
255 upregulated in the distal cluster and 36 genes differentially upregulated in the proximal
256 cluster (**Fig. 4D**). sc-proximal clusters showed high expression of myofibroblast (myCAF)
257 marker genes including *MMP11* and *HOPX* whilst the distal population was enriched for
258 expression of genes associated with inflammatory CAF (iCAF) such as *CXCL12* and *CFD* (**Fig.**
259 **4E**).

260 To investigate the likely functions and master transcription factor regulators that are active
261 for each cluster, differentially enriched pathways, GO-terms and TF target gene sets were
262 identified (Fig. 4F). This showed that sc-proximal fibroblasts are enriched for cell division,
263 chemotaxis and heat shock protein binding. Furthermore, they express a wide range of Wnt
264 ligands including *WNT5A*, *WNT11*, *WNT2*, *WNT5*, *WNT5A* and *WNT5B* (**Fig. 4F,G**). In
265 contrast, sc-distal fibroblasts show enrichment of pathways associated with generation of
266 the extracellular matrix, negative regulation of stem cell proliferation, complement
267 activation and retinoic acid metabolism (**Fig. 4F**). Also notable was expression of many
268 members of the complement pathway as well as many genes associated with retinoic acid
269 metabolism (**Fig. 4G**). The relative gene set enrichment profiles highlight a potential further
270 subcluster within the sc-distant cells which may indicate the presence of transitional cells at
271 the interface between distant and proximal fibroblasts (Fig. 4F).

272 Enrichments of transcription factor target gene sets (regulons) showed considerable
273 divergence and reveals how spatially determined activity of transcription factors could
274 underpin differential fibroblast programming.

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Fig. 4. Proximal and Distal Fibroblast populations identified in single cell transcriptome data of PDAC.

A. Average expression of spatially defined tumor-proximal or tumor-distant stromal genes within cell types defined by scRNA-seq (n=3).

B. UMAP embedding of scRNA-Seq data from fibroblasts overlaid with (left to right) expression of the canonical fibroblast marker genes *DCN*, *LUM* and *THY1*; *COL1A2* found in CAFs; gene set variation analysis (GSVA) signature score for tumor-proximal (*DKK3*, *PDPN*, *PTEN*, *STAT2*, *B2* and *STAT1*) or tumor-distant (*STAT3*, *IL6*, *C3*, *VSIR*, *CD34*, *CSF1R*, *THY1*, *SFRP2*) associated stromal genes; Clustering based on unsupervised Louvain assignment. n=229 Fibroblast cells.

C. Average cluster-wise expression profile of selected proximal and distant stroma associated genes as identified by spatial profiling.

D. Differential expression analysis between sc-proximal and sc-distant fibroblast cells. Colored points indicate differentially expressed genes (BH adjusted p < 0.05 & absolute log₂FC > 0.5).

E. Violin plots depicting cluster-wise expression distribution of canonical myCAF and iCAF marker genes.

294 F. GSVA score profiles identified as differentially enriched (BH adjusted $p < 0.001$) in sc-distant vs sc-
295 proximal cells.

296 G. Average within-cluster expression profile of Complement, Retinoic acid metabolism and Wnt
297 ligand biogenesis gene sets. Grey = no detectable expression.

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299 **Podoplanin and hypoxia predict poor outcome whilst high level expression of immune** 300 **regulatory genes associates with superior clinical outcome**

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302 The study cohort had been selected to comprise patients with poor or good clinical outcome
303 to allow potential identification of spatial transcriptional correlates of disease progression.

304 Poor outcome was defined as death within 1 year whilst patients with good outcome
305 exhibited survival beyond 3 years (**Fig. 5**).

306 Overall gene expression profiles were initially compared between these two groups to
307 define spatially unaware prognostic transcriptional signatures. High level transcriptional
308 expression of *PDPN*, *HIF1A*, *PDL1* (CD274) and *VEGFA* were associated with poor clinical
309 outcome (**Fig. 5A, Figure 5 – figure supplement 1**). Ten genes were upregulated in patients
310 with survival beyond 3 years and were characterized predominantly by immune activation
311 with increased expression of MHC class I and class II, complement C3 and chemokines CCL5
312 and CXCL9. The integrin *ITGB2* (CD18) and *STAT1* also showed increased expression in this
313 group.

314 The spatial expression of these prognosis-associated genes was then assessed across the
315 two risk groups (**Fig. 5B**). To further pinpoint the likely spatially-defined signal contribution
316 of prognostic genes, good vs bad differentially expressed genes were identified from a
317 within Immune region and within Stroma region analysis (**Fig. 5C**). Additionally, within
318 proximal and within distant stroma region analysis assessed the relative contribution to
319 prognostic signals by proximity to tumor (**Fig. 5D**).

320 Patients with a poor outcome expressed *PDPN* broadly across the tumor microenvironment
321 whilst *HIF-1 α* and *VEGF* expression also extended into the distal stromal and immune
322 regions and likely indicates more extensive hypoxia in this subgroup. Proximal-to-distant
323 stroma expression gradients could also be an indicator of prognosis with *CD44*, *CCL5*,
324 *EPCAM* and *HIF1A* all identified as having divergent gradients in Good vs Bad prognosis
325 groups (**Figure 5 – figure supplement 1C**). This further highlights the spreading of *HIF1A* as a
326 feature of poor prognosis. Good prognosis was associated with broad expression of most
327 immunostimulatory and immunoregulatory genes whilst expression of *IL-11* and *HLA-E* was
328 focused within distal stroma (**Fig. 5C,D,E**). Expression of complement C3 and *NKG7*, a
329 regulator of cytotoxic granule release (22) within the immune region was also enhanced in
330 patients with good clinical outcome.

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Fig.5. Survival expression signatures within spatially defined regions of PDAC

A. Differential gene expression from all regions in relation to poor (<1 year) or good (3+ year) survival. Coloured points indicate differentially expressed genes (BH adjusted $p < 0.05$ & absolute $\log_2\text{FC} > 0.25$).

B. Regional expression of survival-associated genes identified in A. Mean \pm SE of mean. PS=Proximal Stroma; DS=Distant Stroma; I=Immune.

C. 3yr/1yr fold change in expression of survival-associated genes within Immune and Stroma regions. (BH adjusted $p < 0.05$ & absolute $\log_2\text{FC} > 0.25$).

D. 3yr/1yr fold change in expression of survival-associated genes within Tumor-Proximal and Tumor-Distal regions. (BH adjusted $p < 0.05$ & absolute $\log_2\text{FC} > 0.25$).

E. Venn displaying overlaps of 3yr vs 1yr survival DEGs (BH adjusted $p < 0.05$ & absolute $\log_2\text{FC} > 0.25$) within tumor-proximal stroma (PS), tumor-distal stroma (DS) and Immune (I) regions.

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350 A graphical summary (Fig. 6) of the combined Nanostring nCounter and scRNA data analysis
 351 highlights these key data-defined characteristics of spatially determined regions within the
 352 PDAC tumor microenvironment.
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354 **Fig.6. Graphical summary of the transcriptional features of spatially-defined regions in the PDAC**
 355 **tumor microenvironment.**
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358 **Discussion**

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 360 Increased understanding of the pancreatic ductal adenocarcinoma microenvironment is
 361 essential for the development of targeted therapies. Here we combined spatial and single
 362 cell transcriptomic analysis to interrogate patterns of cellular transcription in relation to
 363 tumor proximity and related this to clinical outcome. This reveals spatially-determined
 364 transcriptional programming of fibroblasts with potential opportunities for therapeutic
 365 development.

366 Proximity to tumor was seen to be a strong determinant of transcriptional activity of
 367 stromal cells. In particular, DKK3 and PDPN were both increased markedly on tumor-
 368 proximal cells. PDPN expression is strongly enhanced on cancer-associated fibroblasts in
 369 PDAC (20) and high expression levels are correlated with poor prognosis in some, but not
 370 all, studies (10). DKK3 is a Wnt regulator and is emerging as a potentially important
 371 therapeutic target (18). A range of genes showed increased expression within stromal
 372 populations distal from tumor including the C3 component of complement and SFRP2, a
 373 soluble modulator of Wnt signaling. CD34, a marker of stromal stem cells, was also
 374 expressed more highly in this region and may indicate spatial differentiation of stromal cells
 375 towards the tumor. Due to the nature of two-dimensional imaging, we cannot rule out that
 376 cancer cells may be present above or below the plane of the tissue section. Nonetheless,

377 clear differences between stromal populations were observed suggesting that this potential
378 occurrence did not significantly impact our analysis.

379

380 Integration of spatially-defined transcription signatures with an additional single cell RNA-
381 Seq dataset allowed development of a transcriptional atlas of proximal and distal stromal
382 cells. Tumor-proximal populations displayed features typical of myofibroblasts whilst more
383 distal populations had an inflammatory profile, in line with previous reports (14).
384 Myofibroblast markers included the potent pro-tumorigenic chemokine CXCL14 (23) and
385 WNT5A which may contribute to the differentiation of adipocytes to CAFs (24). Indeed, Wnt
386 ligand signaling plays a key role in PDAC progression and therapeutic resistance, and tumor-
387 proximal fibroblasts are seen to be strong contributors to the Wnt ligand pool with high
388 level expression of the ligands WNT5A, WNT11, WNT2, WNT5, WNT5A and WNT5B.
389 Transcriptional regulation of cell division was also increased, suggesting enhanced
390 proliferation of stromal cells when locally exposed to tumor and in line with prior reports
391 (25).

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393 In contrast, stromal cells located more distally from tumor retained functions such as
394 generation of extracellular matrix protein. Striking expression of a wide range of
395 complement proteins was also seen at this site. CAF populations expressing complement
396 proteins have been observed previously in PDAC (26) and overlap with the transcriptional
397 profile of inflammatory CAF. However, there remains debate as to their potential additional
398 expression within myeloid lineages and high dimensional immunofluorescence analysis may
399 help to resolve this. The physiological role of intracellular complement expression is
400 receiving considerable interest with evidence that it may impact on immune surveillance in
401 pre-clinical models (27). THY1 is not a canonical fibroblast marker but is typically expressed
402 on subsets of myofibroblasts and here we also observed increased levels in the tumor-distal
403 region. Interestingly, we find expression of inflammatory genes in some tumor distal α SMA+
404 regions and it is tempting to speculate that this could represent a potential hybrid
405 myofibroblastic/inflammatory CAF state.

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407 A further finding of note was increased expression of a range of genes associated with
408 retinoids. Vitamin A-containing lipid droplets are known to be enriched within quiescent
409 pancreatic stellate cells in close proximity to the basal aspect of pancreatic acinar cells (28)
410 and, as such, the increased retinoic acid signature in tumor-distal fibroblasts could indicate
411 that these are less activated. Indeed, patients with PDAC are often vitamin A deficient
412 whilst retinoic acid treatment can suppress stellate cell proliferation with associated
413 reduction in Wnt- β -catenin signaling and localized tumor apoptosis (29). ATRA treatment
414 has been shown to be tolerable in patients with advanced disease and is under investigation
415 in phase I trials (30). Distal populations were also enriched for expression of genes
416 associated with negative regulation of stem cell proliferation and may indicate a potential
417 role for cells within this environment in limiting tumor cell progression.

418

419 CAF populations exhibit extreme plasticity and factors such as IL-1 and TGF- β are emerging
420 as important mediators of local phenotype (31). Analysis of relative transcription factor
421 binding expression within tumor-proximal or distal stroma identified substantial differences
422 in transcription factor activity at the two sites. A wide range of transcription factor target

423 were differentially expressed and indicate the importance of local cellular environments in
424 exploiting the transcriptional plasticity of fibroblasts.

425 The study cohort had been selected to include patients with poor or good clinical outcome,
426 based on survival below 1 year or above 3 years respectively. High level expression of
427 podoplanin, HIF-1 α and VEGF were associated with poor outcome. The negative prognostic
428 impact of podoplanin expression in PDAC has been documented previously (10) and
429 podoplanin-positive stromal cells enhance invasion and proliferation of tumor cells.
430 However, downregulation of podoplanin expression does not reverse this effect indicating
431 an important role for additional pathways within this population (20). PDAC disease
432 progression following surgical resection is usually related to metastasis or local progression
433 and the potential role of different fibroblast subsets in the development of the metastatic
434 niche requires further investigation (32).

435 Expression of HIF-1 α is reflective of the hypoxic environment within PDAC tumors and
436 indicates that the intensity of hypoxia is an independent determinant of clinical outcome
437 (33-35). Indeed, spatial extension of HIF-1 α expression into distal stroma and immune
438 microenvironments was an additional risk factor and indicates that the breadth of hypoxia is
439 of prognostic importance. HIF-1 α expression in PDAC is associated with a range of features
440 including enrichment of glycolysis, modulation of mTORC1 and MYC signaling, and immune
441 suppression (36,37). As such, this represents a challenging tumor subgroup for therapeutic
442 intervention although the introduction of HIF-1 α inhibitors offers encouragement in this
443 regard (38). Hypoxia is also likely to explain increased levels of VEGF expression in patients
444 with poor prognosis. VEGF-targeted therapies have not shown significant utility in PDAC but
445 could potentially be considered as part of a multi-modal therapeutic approach (39).

446 In contrast, many immunoregulatory and immunostimulatory genes were increased in
447 patients with good prognosis and concur with studies showing that the extent of
448 lymphocytic infiltration is a favorable indicator for outcome. Liudahl et al. used chromogen-
449 based multiplexed immunohistochemistry (mIHC) to generate an atlas of leucocyte
450 contexture within PDAC (40) and extended prognostic utility to immune subpopulations. It
451 was noteworthy that elevated expression of HLA class II genes was seen in patients with
452 longer term survival and as this association extended into stromal regions it may indicate an
453 important role for HLA-DR+ antigen-presenting CAF (ApCAF) populations (41). Expression of
454 complement protein C3 was associated with good clinical outcome and indicates that this
455 pathway can also help to contain tumor growth (42) despite early indications of a potential
456 pro-tumorigenic role (27). Indeed, the beneficial effect of ApCAF in lung cancer is mediated
457 partially through expression of complement proteins which rescue intratumoral T cells from
458 exhaustion (43) and this may provide a unifying explanation for the prognostic value of HLA
459 class II and complement expression in this study.

460 Expression of IL-11 within distal stroma was also a positive prognostic sign and is
461 noteworthy given a previous report of a similar association with elevated serum
462 concentrations (44). IL-11 is an inflammatory protein within the IL-6 family and as such
463 further analysis of the mechanisms by which it can help to contain PDAC development
464 would be valuable. High level expression of NKG7 within immune regions was also beneficial
465 and, given its central role in regulation of cytotoxic granule release (22), this is noteworthy
466 given its emerging role as a predictive factor in response to checkpoint protein inhibition

467 (45). Overall, the transcriptional correlates of good prognosis clearly identify immunological
468 processes as the central determinant of clinical outcome and augur well for therapeutic
469 interventions that can unmask this immune potential. Immune checkpoint inhibition has
470 been largely unsuccessful for this patient subgroup but there is clearly latent
471 immunogenicity within the PDAC microenvironment and the use of agonistic anti-CD40
472 antibodies has shown promise in clinical studies (46).

473 A limitation of the study is that tumors are markedly heterogeneous and as such our
474 findings may not be representative of the complete architecture. However, to overcome
475 this we used a broad patient cohort and selected regions of interest from across the
476 biopsies. Multiplex immunohistochemical analysis will also be of value to confirm co-
477 expression of proteins within cell subsets.

478 In conclusion, we find that transcriptional activity of stromal subsets is strongly regulated by
479 their relative proximity to tumor and define the transcriptional landscape in relation to
480 spatial localization. Hypoxia is a correlate of poor outcome whilst approaches to enhance
481 the inflammatory environment of distal stroma could offer strategies to improve the clinical
482 outcome for this patient group. Indeed, successful therapy for PDAC may require multi-
483 modal approaches such as HIF inhibition with immune checkpoint blockade (47) or
484 personalized vaccine regimens (48).

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488 **Materials and Methods**

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490 **Participants**

491

492 FFPE tissue from 25 treatment-naïve patients undergoing pylorus-preserving pancreatico-
493 duodenectomy (PPPD) who presented with localized disease were selected for this study.
494 Samples were obtained from the Birmingham Human Biomaterials Resource Centre HBRC (HTA
495 Licence 12358) ethically approved North West - Haydock Research Ethics Committee; Ref
496 20/NW/0001, local ethics number 18-304.

497

498 **Sample processing**

499

500 FFPE tissue blocks were sectioned at 5-µm thickness, deparaffinized and rehydrated using
501 conventional methods. The slides were profiled using NanoString GeoMx Digital Spatial RNA
502 Profiling (DSP) platform through the Technology Access Program (TAP) by Nanostring
503 (Seattle, WA, USA). Briefly, immunofluorescent antibody staining was performed with tissue
504 morphology markers a-SMA, Syto83, Pan-CK and CD45 (Table 1).
505

Name	Channel	Host	Company	Clone #	Catalog #	Concentration used
SMA	488	Mouse	Invitrogen	1A4	53-9760-82	1:200
Syto83	532		Thermo fisher			400nM
PanCk	594	Mouse	Novus	AE1/AE3	NBP2-33200DL594	1:500
CD45	647	Mouse	Novus	2B11+PD7/26	NBP2-34528AF647	1:200

506

Table 1. Morphology marker antibodies

507

508 In parallel, slides were stained with a panel of photocleavable RNA probes. Custom regions
509 of interest (ROI) were selected based on these markers to generate specific domains
510 including ‘tumor-proximal stroma’, tumor-distal stroma’ and ‘immune enriched’ areas.
511 ‘Tumor-proximal stroma’ refers to regions within the tumor that are surrounded by tumor
512 epithelium, while "tumor-distal stroma" refers to regions that are located as far away as
513 possible from malignant ducts and lack surrounding epithelium.

514

515 To minimise the confounding effect of tumor heterogeneity, four ROI were selected for each
516 domain per slide. UV-cleavable probes within each ROI were liberated by UV light,
517 hybridized to optical fluorescent barcodes then counted on the Ncounter to determine the
518 absolute number of mRNA transcripts.

519

520 **NanoString nCounter data analysis**

521

522 Raw NanoString nCounter data expression matrix (**Source Data 1**) was processed following
523 the normalization and quality control procedures as described elsewhere (49). Due to a
524 redundancy in the tags used for both IFNG and ACTA2, data from these probes had to be
525 removed from further analysis. Correlations of housekeeping gene expression across all
526 ROIs were assessed to select the most correlated housekeeping probes H3F3A and UBB to
527 use for downstream normalization (**Supp. Fig. S2A**). Unwanted variation was removed using
528 the R package RUVSeq (50). Firstly, distributional differences were scaled between lanes

529 using upper-quartile normalization then unwanted technical factors were estimated in the
530 resulting gene expression data with the RUVg function selecting H3F3A and UBB as the
531 negative control genes and the number of dimensions of unwanted variation to remove set
532 to 1. A variance stabilizing transformation of the original count data was computed using
533 DESeq2 (51) and estimated unwanted variation was removed using the removeBatchEffects
534 function from limma (52). RLE plots were used to detect any potential outliers before and
535 after normalization (**Supp. Fig. S2B**).

536

537 Differential expression analysis was conducted to compare Immune vs stromal regions, 3 yr
538 vs 1 yr survival and tumor-proximal vs tumor-distant stromal regions using DESeq2,
539 adjusting for multiple testing with Benjamini-Hochberg (BH) procedure. Differentially
540 expressed genes were determined by BH adjusted $p < 0.05$ and absolute $\log_2FC > 0.25$.

541

542 Dimensionality reduction by Uniform Manifold Approximation and Projection (UMAP) was
543 performed on the normalized counts matrix with the umap R package and ggplot2 utilized
544 for plotting. Heatmap visualizations were generated using the ComplexHeatmap package.
545 Pearson correlation was calculated and plots generated using ggpairs and ggcorr functions
546 from the R package GGally.

547

548 **scRNA-Seq data analysis**

549

550 Genes of interest identified from nCounter data analysis were further explored for their
551 expression profiles in single cell RNA sequencing data (GEO accession GSE210199) of cells
552 within the tumor microenvironment of 3 PDAC patients (17).

553

554 *Raw read data processing*

555

556 Raw reads were processed using CellRanger (10X Genomics, v3) functions mkfastq and
557 count. Raw bcl files were converted to fastq and aligned to the human reference genome
558 GRCh38. Gene expression matrices for each patient were analyzed by R software (v3.6).
559 Data pre-processing, QC, dimensionality reduction, clustering and subsequent downstream
560 analysis was performed using the Seurat package (v3.1.1).

561

562 *Data integration and clustering*

563

564 Data from 3 PDAC patient samples was integrated following Seurat SCTransform Integrate
565 Data workflow using the top 3000 most variable genes as integration features. Principal
566 Component Analysis (PCA) was applied and Uniform Manifold Approximation and Projection
567 (UMAP) embedding determined using PCs 1:20. For unsupervised clustering, a shared
568 nearest neighbour graph based on Euclidean distance in PCA space was constructed using
569 Seurat FindNeighbours function and the modules within this graph representing clusters
570 were identified using the 18ouvain algorithm with Seurat FindClusters.

571

572 To annotate clusters with high-level cell type, canonical cell type marker gene expression
573 level was assessed.

574

575 *scRNA-Seq Fibroblast data analysis*

576

577 Transcriptome data was subset taking Fibroblast cells only and unsupervised clustering re-
578 applied on Fibroblasts alone. Expression profile of stromal expressed genes identified from
579 the nCounter dataset to be associated with tumor proximal or tumor-distant regions was
580 assessed within the Fibroblast scRNA-Seq data. These tumor-proximal and tumor-distant
581 gene signatures were scored using GSVA to assess likely tumor-proximal and tumor-distant
582 fibroblasts. Expression profiling and GSVA signature scoring were used to annotate
583 fibroblast subpopulations identified through clustering as “Proximal-like” and “Distant-like”.

584

585 To expand the pool of possible transcriptional markers for tumor proximal and tumor
586 distant fibroblasts, differential expression analysis was conducted comparing Proximal-like
587 and Distant-like clusters using findMarkers with MAST option (test.use=“MAST”), which uses
588 a hurdle model tailored to scRNA-Seq data. MAST is a two-part GLM that simultaneously
589 models how many cells express the gene by logistic regression and the expression level by
590 Gaussian distribution (53). Differential expression testing was performed using the
591 likelihood ratio test. Differentially expressed genes were determined by Benjamini Hochberg
592 adjusted $p < 0.05$ and absolute $\log_2FC > 0.5$.

593

594

595

596

597 **References**

598

- 599 1. Arnold M, Rutherford MJ, Bardot A, Ferlay J, Andersson TM, Myklebust TA, *et al.*
600 Progress in cancer survival, mortality, and incidence in seven high-income countries
601 1995-2014 (ICBP SURVMARK-2): a population-based study. *Lancet Oncol*
602 **2019**;20(11):1493-505 doi 10.1016/S1470-2045(19)30456-5.
- 603 2. Biffi G, Tuveson DA. Diversity and Biology of Cancer-Associated Fibroblasts.
604 *Physiol Rev* **2021**;101(1):147-76 doi 10.1152/physrev.00048.2019.
- 605 3. Menezes S, Okail MH, Jalil SMA, Kocher HM, Cameron AJM. Cancer-associated
606 fibroblasts in pancreatic cancer: new subtypes, new markers, new targets. *J Pathol*
607 **2022**;257(4):526-44 doi 10.1002/path.5926.
- 608 4. Piersma B, Hayward MK, Weaver VM. Fibrosis and cancer: A strained relationship.
609 *Biochim Biophys Acta Rev Cancer* **2020**;1873(2):188356 doi
610 10.1016/j.bbcan.2020.188356.
- 611 5. Mhaidly R, Mechta-Grigoriou F. Role of cancer-associated fibroblast subpopulations
612 in immune infiltration, as a new means of treatment in cancer. *Immunol Rev*
613 **2021**;302(1):259-72 doi 10.1111/imr.12978.
- 614 6. Inoue T, Adachi K, Kawana K, Taguchi A, Nagamatsu T, Fujimoto A, *et al.* Cancer-
615 associated fibroblast suppresses killing activity of natural killer cells through
616 downregulation of poliovirus receptor (PVR/CD155), a ligand of activating NK
617 receptor. *Int J Oncol* **2016**;49(4):1297-304 doi 10.3892/ijo.2016.3631.
- 618 7. Ene-Obong A, Clear AJ, Watt J, Wang J, Fatah R, Riches JC, *et al.* Activated
619 pancreatic stellate cells sequester CD8+ T cells to reduce their infiltration of the
620 juxtatumoral compartment of pancreatic ductal adenocarcinoma. *Gastroenterology*
621 **2013**;145(5):1121-32 doi 10.1053/j.gastro.2013.07.025.
- 622 8. Kumar V, Donthireddy L, Marvel D, Condamine T, Wang F, Lavilla-Alonso S, *et al.*
623 Cancer-Associated Fibroblasts Neutralize the Anti-tumor Effect of CSF1 Receptor
624 Blockade by Inducing PMN-MDSC Infiltration of Tumors. *Cancer Cell*
625 **2017**;32(5):654-68 e5 doi 10.1016/j.ccell.2017.10.005.
- 626 9. Albregues J, Meneguzzi G, Gaggioli C. [Carcinoma-associated fibroblasts in cancer:
627 the great escape]. *Med Sci (Paris)* **2014**;30(4):391-7 doi
628 10.1051/medsci/20143004012.
- 629 10. Mezawa Y, Orimo A. The roles of tumor- and metastasis-promoting carcinoma-
630 associated fibroblasts in human carcinomas. *Cell Tissue Res* **2016**;365(3):675-89 doi
631 10.1007/s00441-016-2471-1.
- 632 11. Fang Y, Zhou W, Rong Y, Kuang T, Xu X, Wu W, *et al.* Exosomal miRNA-106b
633 from cancer-associated fibroblast promotes gemcitabine resistance in pancreatic
634 cancer. *Exp Cell Res* **2019**;383(1):111543 doi 10.1016/j.yexcr.2019.111543.
- 635 12. Ozdemir BC, Pentcheva-Hoang T, Carstens JL, Zheng X, Wu CC, Simpson TR, *et al.*
636 Depletion of carcinoma-associated fibroblasts and fibrosis induces
637 immunosuppression and accelerates pancreas cancer with reduced survival. *Cancer*
638 *Cell* **2014**;25(6):719-34 doi 10.1016/j.ccr.2014.04.005.
- 639 13. Catenacci DV, Junttila MR, Karrison T, Bahary N, Horiba MN, Nattam SR, *et al.*
640 Randomized Phase Ib/II Study of Gemcitabine Plus Placebo or Vismodegib, a
641 Hedgehog Pathway Inhibitor, in Patients With Metastatic Pancreatic Cancer. *J Clin*
642 *Oncol* **2015**;33(36):4284-92 doi 10.1200/JCO.2015.62.8719.
- 643 14. Ohlund D, Handly-Santana A, Biffi G, Elyada E, Almeida AS, Ponz-Sarvise M, *et al.*
644 Distinct populations of inflammatory fibroblasts and myofibroblasts in pancreatic
645 cancer. *J Exp Med* **2017**;214(3):579-96 doi 10.1084/jem.20162024.

- 646 15. Dominguez CX, Muller S, Keerthivasan S, Koeppen H, Hung J, Gierke S, *et al.*
647 Single-Cell RNA Sequencing Reveals Stromal Evolution into LRRC15(+)
648 Myofibroblasts as a Determinant of Patient Response to Cancer Immunotherapy.
649 *Cancer Discov* **2020**;10(2):232-53 doi 10.1158/2159-8290.CD-19-0644.
- 650 16. Neuzillet C, Tijeras-Raballand A, Ragulan C, Cros J, Patil Y, Martinet M, *et al.* Inter-
651 and intra-tumoral heterogeneity in cancer-associated fibroblasts of human pancreatic
652 ductal adenocarcinoma. *J Pathol* **2019**;248(1):51-65 doi 10.1002/path.5224.
- 653 17. Pearce H, Croft W, Nicol SM, Margielewska-Davies S, Powell R, Cornall R, *et al.*
654 Tissue-resident memory T cells in pancreatic ductal adenocarcinoma co-express PD-1
655 and TIGIT and functional inhibition is reversible by dual antibody blockade. *Cancer*
656 *Immunol Res* **2023** doi 10.1158/2326-6066.CIR-22-0121.
- 657 18. Zhou L, Husted H, Moore T, Lu M, Deng D, Liu Y, *et al.* Suppression of stromal-
658 derived Dickkopf-3 (DKK3) inhibits tumor progression and prolongs survival in
659 pancreatic ductal adenocarcinoma. *Sci Transl Med* **2018**;10(464) doi
660 10.1126/scitranslmed.aat3487.
- 661 19. Hirayama K, Kono H, Nakata Y, Akazawa Y, Wakana H, Fukushima H, *et al.*
662 Expression of podoplanin in stromal fibroblasts plays a pivotal role in the prognosis
663 of patients with pancreatic cancer. *Surg Today* **2018**;48(1):110-8 doi 10.1007/s00595-
664 017-1559-x.
- 665 20. Shindo K, Aishima S, Ohuchida K, Fujiwara K, Fujino M, Mizuuchi Y, *et al.*
666 Podoplanin expression in cancer-associated fibroblasts enhances tumor progression of
667 invasive ductal carcinoma of the pancreas. *Mol Cancer* **2013**;12(1):168 doi
668 10.1186/1476-4598-12-168.
- 669 21. Shi J, Lu P, Shen W, He R, Yang MW, Fang Y, *et al.* CD90 highly expressed
670 population harbors a stemness signature and creates an immunosuppressive niche in
671 pancreatic cancer. *Cancer Lett* **2019**;453:158-69 doi 10.1016/j.canlet.2019.03.051.
- 672 22. Ng SS, De Labastida Rivera F, Yan J, Corvino D, Das I, Zhang P, *et al.* The NK cell
673 granule protein NKG7 regulates cytotoxic granule exocytosis and inflammation. *Nat*
674 *Immunol* **2020**;21(10):1205-18 doi 10.1038/s41590-020-0758-6.
- 675 23. Augsten M, Sjoberg E, Frings O, Vorrink SU, Frijhoff J, Olsson E, *et al.* Cancer-
676 associated fibroblasts expressing CXCL14 rely upon NOS1-derived nitric oxide
677 signaling for their tumor-supporting properties. *Cancer Res* **2014**;74(11):2999-3010
678 doi 10.1158/0008-5472.CAN-13-2740.
- 679 24. Zoico E, Darra E, Rizzatti V, Budui S, Franceschetti G, Mazzali G, *et al.* Adipocytes
680 WNT5a mediated dedifferentiation: a possible target in pancreatic cancer
681 microenvironment. *Oncotarget* **2016**;7(15):20223-35 doi 10.18632/oncotarget.7936.
- 682 25. Kalluri R, Zeisberg M. Fibroblasts in cancer. *Nat Rev Cancer* **2006**;6(5):392-401 doi
683 10.1038/nrc1877.
- 684 26. Chen K, Wang Q, Li M, Guo H, Liu W, Wang F, *et al.* Single-cell RNA-seq reveals
685 dynamic change in tumor microenvironment during pancreatic ductal adenocarcinoma
686 malignant progression. *EBioMedicine* **2021**;66:103315 doi
687 10.1016/j.ebiom.2021.103315.
- 688 27. Kwak JW, Laskowski J, Li HY, McSharry MV, Sippel TR, Bullock BL, *et al.*
689 Complement Activation via a C3a Receptor Pathway Alters CD4(+) T Lymphocytes
690 and Mediates Lung Cancer Progression. *Cancer Res* **2018**;78(1):143-56 doi
691 10.1158/0008-5472.CAN-17-0240.
- 692 28. Erkan M, Adler G, Apte MV, Bachem MG, Buchholz M, Detlefsen S, *et al.*
693 StellaTUM: current consensus and discussion on pancreatic stellate cell research. *Gut*
694 **2012**;61(2):172-8 doi 10.1136/gutjnl-2011-301220.

- 695 29. Froeling FE, Feig C, Chelala C, Dobson R, Mein CE, Tuveson DA, *et al.* Retinoic
696 acid-induced pancreatic stellate cell quiescence reduces paracrine Wnt-beta-catenin
697 signaling to slow tumor progression. *Gastroenterology* **2011**;141(4):1486-97, 97 e1-
698 14 doi 10.1053/j.gastro.2011.06.047.
- 699 30. Kocher HM, Basu B, Froeling FEM, Sarker D, Slater S, Carlin D, *et al.* Phase I
700 clinical trial repurposing all-trans retinoic acid as a stromal targeting agent for
701 pancreatic cancer. *Nat Commun* **2020**;11(1):4841 doi 10.1038/s41467-020-18636-w.
- 702 31. Biffi G, Oni TE, Spielman B, Hao Y, Elyada E, Park Y, *et al.* IL1-Induced
703 JAK/STAT Signaling Is Antagonized by TGFbeta to Shape CAF Heterogeneity in
704 Pancreatic Ductal Adenocarcinoma. *Cancer Discov* **2019**;9(2):282-301 doi
705 10.1158/2159-8290.CD-18-0710.
- 706 32. Xu Z, Vonlaufen A, Phillips PA, Fiala-Beer E, Zhang X, Yang L, *et al.* Role of
707 pancreatic stellate cells in pancreatic cancer metastasis. *Am J Pathol*
708 **2010**;177(5):2585-96 doi 10.2353/ajpath.2010.090899.
- 709 33. Ye LY, Zhang Q, Bai XL, Pankaj P, Hu QD, Liang TB. Hypoxia-inducible factor
710 1alpha expression and its clinical significance in pancreatic cancer: a meta-analysis.
711 *Pancreatology* **2014**;14(5):391-7 doi 10.1016/j.pan.2014.06.008.
- 712 34. Chen D, Huang H, Zang L, Gao W, Zhu H, Yu X. Development and Verification of
713 the Hypoxia- and Immune-Associated Prognostic Signature for Pancreatic Ductal
714 Adenocarcinoma. *Front Immunol* **2021**;12:728062 doi 10.3389/fimmu.2021.728062.
- 715 35. Hao J. HIF-1 is a critical target of pancreatic cancer. *Oncoimmunology*
716 **2015**;4(9):e1026535 doi 10.1080/2162402X.2015.1026535.
- 717 36. Zhuang H, Wang S, Chen B, Zhang Z, Ma Z, Li Z, *et al.* Prognostic Stratification
718 Based on HIF-1 Signaling for Evaluating Hypoxic Status and Immune Infiltration in
719 Pancreatic Ductal Adenocarcinomas. *Front Immunol* **2021**;12:790661 doi
720 10.3389/fimmu.2021.790661.
- 721 37. Zhao X, Gao S, Ren H, Sun W, Zhang H, Sun J, *et al.* Hypoxia-inducible factor-1
722 promotes pancreatic ductal adenocarcinoma invasion and metastasis by activating
723 transcription of the actin-bundling protein fascin. *Cancer Res* **2014**;74(9):2455-64 doi
724 10.1158/0008-5472.CAN-13-3009.
- 725 38. Semenza GL. Regulation of Erythropoiesis by the Hypoxia-Inducible Factor Pathway:
726 Effects of Genetic and Pharmacological Perturbations. *Annu Rev Med* **2022** doi
727 10.1146/annurev-med-042921-102602.
- 728 39. Cabebe E, Fisher GA. Clinical trials of VEGF receptor tyrosine kinase inhibitors in
729 pancreatic cancer. *Expert Opin Investig Drugs* **2007**;16(4):467-76 doi
730 10.1517/13543784.16.4.467.
- 731 40. Liudahl SM, Betts CB, Sivagnanam S, Morales-Oyarvide V, da Silva A, Yuan C, *et al.*
732 Leukocyte Heterogeneity in Pancreatic Ductal Adenocarcinoma: Phenotypic and
733 Spatial Features Associated with Clinical Outcome. *Cancer Discov* **2021**;11(8):2014-
734 31 doi 10.1158/2159-8290.CD-20-0841.
- 735 41. Elyada E, Bolisetty M, Laise P, Flynn WF, Courtois ET, Burkhart RA, *et al.* Cross-
736 Species Single-Cell Analysis of Pancreatic Ductal Adenocarcinoma Reveals Antigen-
737 Presenting Cancer-Associated Fibroblasts. *Cancer Discov* **2019**;9(8):1102-23 doi
738 10.1158/2159-8290.CD-19-0094.
- 739 42. Revel M, Daugan MV, Sautes-Fridman C, Fridman WH, Roumenina LT.
740 Complement System: Promoter or Suppressor of Cancer Progression? *Antibodies*
741 (Basel) **2020**;9(4) doi 10.3390/antib9040057.
- 742 43. Kerdidani D, Aerakis E, Verrou KM, Angelidis I, Douka K, Maniou MA, *et al.* Lung
743 tumor MHCII immunity depends on in situ antigen presentation by fibroblasts. *J Exp*
744 *Med* **2022**;219(2) doi 10.1084/jem.20210815.

- 745 44. Ren C, Chen Y, Han C, Fu D, Chen H. Plasma interleukin-11 (IL-11) levels have
746 diagnostic and prognostic roles in patients with pancreatic cancer. *Tumor Biol*
747 **2014**;35(11):11467-72 doi 10.1007/s13277-014-2459-y.
- 748 45. Wen T, Barham W, Li Y, Zhang H, Gicobi JK, Hirdler JB, *et al.* NKG7 Is a T-cell-
749 Intrinsic Therapeutic Target for Improving Antitumor Cytotoxicity and Cancer
750 Immunotherapy. *Cancer Immunol Res* **2022**;10(2):162-81 doi 10.1158/2326-
751 6066.CIR-21-0539.
- 752 46. Byrne KT, Betts CB, Mick R, Sivagnanam S, Bajor DL, Laheru DA, *et al.*
753 Neoadjuvant Selicrelumab, an Agonist CD40 Antibody, Induces Changes in the
754 Tumor Microenvironment in Patients with Resectable Pancreatic Cancer. *Clin Cancer*
755 *Res* **2021**;27(16):4574-86 doi 10.1158/1078-0432.CCR-21-1047.
- 756 47. Salman S, Meyers DJ, Wicks EE, Lee SN, Datan E, Thomas AM, *et al.* HIF inhibitor
757 32-134D eradicates murine hepatocellular carcinoma in combination with anti-PD1
758 therapy. *J Clin Invest* **2022**;132(9) doi 10.1172/JCI156774.
- 759 48. Rojas LA, Sethna Z, Soares KC, Olcese C, Pang N, Patterson E, *et al.* Personalized
760 RNA neoantigen vaccines stimulate T cells in pancreatic cancer. *Nature*
761 **2023**;618(7963):144-50 doi 10.1038/s41586-023-06063-y.
- 762 49. Bhattacharya A, Hamilton AM, Furberg H, Pietzak E, Purdue MP, Troester MA, *et al.*
763 An approach for normalization and quality control for NanoString RNA expression
764 data. *Brief Bioinform* **2021**;22(3) doi 10.1093/bib/bbaa163.
- 765 50. Risso D, Ngai J, Speed TP, Dudoit S. Normalization of RNA-seq data using factor
766 analysis of control genes or samples. *Nat Biotechnol* **2014**;32(9):896-902 doi
767 10.1038/nbt.2931.
- 768 51. Love MI, Huber W, Anders S. Moderated estimation of fold change and dispersion
769 for RNA-seq data with DESeq2. *Genome Biol* **2014**;15(12):550 doi 10.1186/s13059-
770 014-0550-8.
- 771 52. Ritchie ME, Phipson B, Wu D, Hu Y, Law CW, Shi W, *et al.* limma powers
772 differential expression analyses for RNA-sequencing and microarray studies. *Nucleic*
773 *Acids Res* **2015**;43(7):e47 doi 10.1093/nar/gkv007.
- 774 53. Finak G, McDavid A, Yajima M, Deng J, Gersuk V, Shalek AK, *et al.* MAST: a
775 flexible statistical framework for assessing transcriptional changes and characterizing
776 heterogeneity in single-cell RNA sequencing data. *Genome Biol* **2015**;16:278 doi
777 10.1186/s13059-015-0844-5.
- 778
779

780 **Supplementary File 1**

781

782 **Supplementary File 1. NanoString nCounter RNA hybridisation probeset.** List of RNA probe
783 panels used for Nanostring nCounter data collection including the immunoncology core
784 panel, fibroblast-specific, housekeeping and negative control probe sets.

785

786

787 **Supplementary Figures**

788

789 **Figure 2 – figure supplement 1. Raw count expression profiles.** A, Heatmap of raw
790 expression profile for the complete probeset (colour scale= raw count). B, Per patient (scan)
791 expression distributions for PanCK+ (tumor) and PanCK- (non-tumor) regions of interest. C,
792 Per patient (scan) expression profiles (mean +/- SE) for Endogenous, Housekeeping and
793 Negative control probesets.

794

795 **Figure 2 – figure supplement 2. Housekeeping gene correlations and data normalisation.**
796 A, Pairwise correlation scatter plots for 6 housekeeping control probes. Raw housekeeping
797 gene counts from all regions of interest (ROIs) were correlated against each other. Plots
798 display the scatter, distribution histogram and Pearson correlation coefficient and
799 significance (**p<0.001). B, Relative log expression plots of raw count data and post
800 normalization with the top two most-correlated housekeeping genes (H3F3A and UBB) to
801 remove unwanted variation (RUV method).

802

803 **Figure 2 – figure supplement 3. Correlation Matrix of endogenous probes.** Pairwise
804 correlations of normalized gene count data represented as a matrix of Pearson correlation
805 coefficients.

806

807 **Figure 2 – figure supplement 4. Individual gene expression profiles on UMAP embeddings**
808 **of all regions of interest (ROIs).** UMAP embedding generated from normalized count data
809 of all probes in all REIs overlaid with ROI-specific normalized gene count.

810

811 **Figure 2 – figure supplement 5. High level cell type contexture of PDAC tumor**
812 **microenvironment.** A (left), UMAP embedding of transcriptional data for 17,958 cells in the
813 tumor microenvironment of 3 x PDAC patient tissue samples overlaid with high level cell
814 type identified from unsupervised clustering. A (right), UMAP embedding overlaid with
815 source sample identifier. B, UMAP embedding overlaid with the expression profile of
816 canonical high level cell type marker genes. C. Average scRNA expression profile of spatial
817 profiling defined Immune and Stroma ROI type-associated genes within high level cell types
818 defined by scRNA-seq (n=3 PDAC samples).

819

820 **Figure 3 – figure supplement 1. Correlations of proximity specific markers DKK3 and**
821 **C3.** Pairwise Pearson correlations of tumor-proximity specific markers C3 and DKK3 against
822 marker genes for Lymphocytes, Monocytes and Fibroblast cells. Coefficients are highlighted
823 where there are significant correlations of either DKK3 or C3 within Proximal (green) or
824 Distant (orange) Stroma ROIs.

825

826 **Figure 5 – figure supplement 1. Profile of Survival expression signatures within PDAC TME.**
827 A, Average scRNA expression profile of Survival associated genes within high level cell types
828 of scRNA-seq dataset (n=3). B, Expression profile of Survival associated genes identified by
829 3yr vs 1yr differential expression analysis. C, Proximal Stroma (PS): Distant Stroma (DS)
830 ratios stratified by survival outcome for selected genes with significant difference in ratio
831 when stratified by survival.
832

A

